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A framework for analysing societal impacts of connected and automated transport systems

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1 Background and research problems

The Horizon2020 project Levitate (Societal impacts of Connected and Automated Transport Systems; CATS) has the following objectives:

1. To develop a range of forecasting and backcasting scenarios and baseline conditions relating to the deployment of one or more mobility technologies that will be used as the basis of impact assessments and forecasts. These will cover three primary use cases – automated urban shuttle, passenger cars and freight services.
2. To establish a multi-disciplinary methodology to assess the short, medium and long-term impacts of CATS on mobility, safety, environment, society and other impact areas. Several quantitative indicators will be identified for each impact type
3. To apply the methods and forecast the impact of CATS over the short, medium and long term for a range of use cases, operational design domains and environments and an extensive range of mobility, environmental, safety, economic and societal indicators. A series of case studies will be conducted to validate the methodologies and to demonstrate the system.
4. To incorporate the methods within a new web-based policy support tool to enable city and other authorities to forecast impacts of CATS on urban areas. The methods developed within Levitate will be available within a tool box allowing the impact of measures to be assessed individually. A Decision Support System will enable users to apply backcasting methods to identify the sequences of CATS measures that will result in their desired policy objectives.

The objective of this working paper is to define a framework for analysing the societal impacts of CATS in order to fulfil the objectives stated above. The framework is a conceptual scheme, in which key concepts are defined in theoretical and operational terms and the main causal links to be modelled quantitatively are identified. The paper outlines the major analytic choices to be made and proposes decisions for each of these choices.

The main research problems dealt with in the paper are:

1. What are the independent variables in the study? Which connected and automated systems are included?
2. How can relevant connected and automated systems be defined in analyses referring to the short term, medium term and long term?
3. Which impacts of connected and automated systems should be included in analysis?
4. How can relevant impacts be measured and what are the impacts of specific connected and automated transport systems?

2 Connected and automated transport systems

The proposal lists the following technologies as examples of systems that will be included in the three use cases to be developed. Which of the technologies are relevant, depends on the time horizon of analysis.

Table 1: Example CATS deployment scenarios for each Use Case

Use case	 Freight transport		
Automation scenarios	Point to point shuttle	SAE L2/3/4 automation	Highway platooning
	Anywhere to anywhere shuttle	Highway pilot	Automated urban delivery
	Segregated pathway operations	Autopark	Depot to depot automated transfer
	On road operations	Highway pilot	Automated intermodal transport
	Intermodal route planning	Automatic Cruise Control	Synchronized Traffic Load on bridges
	Street design implications	Traffic jam pilot	Intelligent access control of infrastructure/bridge
		City chauffeur	
Connectivity scenarios		Geo-fencing based powertrain use	Geo-fencing based powertrain use
	Green light optimized speed advisory	Green light optimized speed advisory	Green light optimized speed advisory
		Road use pricing	Road use pricing
	System-aware route optimization	System-aware route optimization	System-aware route optimization
Mobility as a Service	Multi-modal integrated payments	Multi-modal integrated payments	
	e-hailing	Shared ownership models	
	Automated ride sharing	Urban platooning	Local freight consolidation

A distinction has been made between the short term, the medium term and the long term. The short term is within 5 years, medium term 10-15 years and long term 25+ years. It is obviously difficult to predict which technologies will be widely used in the long-term perspective. Rather than relying on a highly uncertain prediction about when different technologies will be available, it is proposed to base analysis on the following assumptions:

In the short term, automated urban transport will only exist in the form of small automated buses as are currently being tested in many cities. The passenger kilometres travelled on these buses will be a small share of public transport in the cities where automated buses are tested, most likely less than 10 %.

In the medium term, automated urban transport will represent a larger share of all urban public transport, although making a definite prediction is not possible. A choice must be made and analysis based on that choice. Analysis will take the form: if it is assumed that X percent of urban public transport is automated, then impacts will be such and such. Functional relationships must be developed to relate the size of impacts to the penetration level of automated transport.

In the long term, it is assumed that all urban transport is fully automated and applies the connectivity solutions listed in Table 1. Again, this assumption should not be interpreted as a forecast of what will actually happen 25 years from now, but as an analytic choice made in order to explore, as far as current knowledge permits, the impacts of fully automated urban public transport.

A similar reasoning applies to the use case for passenger cars. Within the next five years, neither connected nor fully automated cars are likely to be introduced on a wide scale. However, even within the next five years, cars are likely to become safer and more fuel efficient. How much safer and how much more fuel efficient can be predicted reasonably well by extrapolating historical trends. In the medium term, it appears more likely that cars can become connected than fully automated. With a mixture of cars having technology for connecting with other cars and cars not having such technology, it may be necessary to regulate connected driving by having dedicated lanes for such cars or having the possibility of disconnecting cars, for example, to allow pedestrians to cross the road. Although connected cars can be packed more densely than manually driven cars, it is not acceptable to make pedestrians wait for a “train” of, say, 100 connected cars to pass. In the long term, full automation will be assumed – again not necessarily because this a realistic forecast, but because it is of general interest to try to estimate the impacts of fully automated driving, and identify gaps in knowledge that prevent definite conclusions from being drawn.

Technological changes in freight transport may follow broadly the same trajectory as for passenger cars and urban public transport. Adoption of automated vehicles may go faster than for passenger cars, as saving the cost of having a driver will make freight transport cheaper. In the short term, a continued market penetration of level 1 (SAE typology) driver assistance systems is likely and effects can be estimated based on evaluations of these systems. In the medium term, freight vehicles may become connected, but not fully automated. In the long term, analysis will be based on an assumption of full automation.

3 Impacts of connected and automated transport systems

The following list of potential impacts of connected and automated transport systems is taken from the proposal and other relevant publications:

- Safety
- Road capacity
- Infrastructure wear
- Travel time
- Geographic accessibility
- Vehicle kilometres of travel
- Optimisation of route choice
- Vehicle ownership cost
- Vehicle operating costs
- Use and valuation of travel time
- Travel comfort
- Vehicle ownership rates
- Use of shared mobility services
- Shifts in market shares of transport modes
- Land use

Changes in commuting distances
Energy efficiency of transport
Vehicle emissions
Individual accessibility to transport

Below each impact is briefly defined and the most common hypotheses about the effects of connected and automated transport systems are mentioned.

Safety denotes the number of accidents and the number of killed or injured road users. It is commonly assumed that connected and automated vehicles will improve safety. At least the following three factors influence the magnitude of the effect:

1. Not all modes of transport lend themselves to full automation. It is reasonable to expect that pedestrians, cyclists, mopeds, motorcycles, all-terrain vehicles (ATVs), vehicles used in road works (asphalting machines, steamrollers) and possibly agricultural tractors will remain as manual modes of transport.
2. The reliability of hardware and software used in automated vehicles. Although first generation software may contain errors, it is expected that a systematic use of machine learning will rapidly correct errors and make software very reliable.
3. The risk of cyberattacks on connected and automated vehicles. This risk cannot be ruled out, although quantifying it is impossible. It is, to some extent, possible to simulate cyberattacks and model their potential effects.

How safety effects can be estimated numerically is discussed in section 4 of the paper.

Road capacity is the number of vehicles that can pass a section of road per unit of time. It is commonly assumed that connected and automated vehicles will effectively increase road capacity (i.e. increase capacity without changing the layout of the road) by being able to keep shorter distances and possibly also by being smaller than current vehicles. The full benefits of more densely packed vehicles can only be realised when all vehicles are fully automated and driven autonomously (i.e. without the need for driver intervention). As long as there are vehicles operated by humans, allowance must be made for their reaction time. Short headways will then only be possible in dedicated lanes where manually driven vehicles are not allowed to enter.

Travel time is the duration of a trip of a given length. The most common expectation is that automation of transport will shorten travel time, by increasing road capacity and by optimising route choice. Nevertheless, the full picture is more complex. Automated vehicles need to find ways of interacting with non-automated road users in ways that are not too time-consuming. A pedestrian stepping in front of an automated bus can force it to stop; if the pedestrian decides to stay put, the bus will be stranded for as long as it takes. Interaction needs to become considerably more sophisticated than this to keep traffic flowing. Moreover, even if in-vehicle time on a given trip becomes shorter, total travel time need not become shorter, if there is a widespread use of shared mobility. This will resemble public transport in the sense that users may need to wait for a vehicle to arrive.

Communication systems will surely minimise waiting times, but if vehicles are shared with other travellers, one cannot expect them to be instantly available at all locations. Of course, trip planning (booking the vehicle some time before leaving the office) can bring waiting times close to zero.

The geographic accessibility of a location is characterised by the time it takes to travel to the location from other locations. If travel times become shorter, given locations may become more accessible by becoming possible to reach in less time. This could make the locations more attractive both for business and as places to live. One can describe the

accessibility of a location by means of concentric iso-travel time curves surrounding it. The larger the (mean) radius of an iso-time curve, the more accessible is the location.

Vehicle kilometres of travel is the number of kilometres travelled by vehicles on public roads during a given period of time. Most studies predict that automated transport will increase vehicle kilometres of travel, chiefly by reducing the generalised costs of travel. This prediction seems quite reasonable if individual vehicle ownership remains common. Yet, from a societal perspective, individual vehicle ownership is an ineffective transport system, since a car, on the average, is parked about 23 out of 24 hours. If use of the car was shared between many individuals, it might operate considerably more than about 1 hour per day. A smaller number of shared cars could then serve the same number of individual trips as a larger number of cars each with a single occupant only do today. The net effect on vehicle kilometres of travel is difficult to predict. Half the number of cars each travelling twice the distance makes for no change in the total number of vehicle kilometres of travel. Definite predictions are impossible to make with any confidence. Impacts need to be modelled in terms of scenarios which have the following logical structure: IF (we assume such and such) THEN (impacts will be such and such).

Route choice can be optimised according to several criteria. As fully automated vehicles will presumably have access to true-time data on travel times on different routes, they should be able to choose the shortest route. This may allocate traffic to different routes so as to minimise total travel times. However, in order to estimate any gain associated with this, one needs to know how far current route choices deviate from the optimal. Traffic simulation, calibrated to real data on volume and delay, may perhaps provide a basis for estimating effects.

The costs of vehicle ownership consist of the cost of buying the vehicle and its loss in value as it gets older. The most common assumption seems to be that fully automated vehicles will be more expensive than current vehicles. This, by itself, may encourage more widespread car sharing. All else equal, an increase in the price of a commodity tends to reduce demand for it. One may probably rely on published demand elasticities to estimate the effect of more expensive vehicles.

Vehicle operating costs are the total costs, per kilometre of travel, of operating a vehicle. These costs are expected to become lower when vehicles become automated or autonomous. One reason is that energy efficiency is expected to increase, in particular if electric vehicles replace fossil fuel vehicles. Furthermore, platooning vehicles will reduce drag and further improve energy efficiency. Professional transport will become cheaper when a driver is no longer needed. Available elasticities can be applied to estimate how a reduction in vehicle operating costs will influence travel demand.

Today, time spent as a driver cannot be used for much else than driving. One can listen to the radio, but most other potential distractions are too dangerous to contemplate. If vehicles are fully autonomous, never needing a driver to intervene, time spent in the vehicle can be used for other activities like working or relaxing. The time spent in the vehicle may then be regarded as less wasteful and the value of travel time savings may decline. This will in turn influence the returns on road investments, as travel time savings have traditionally constituted the major part of the benefits of new or improved roads.

Travel comfort is a multidimensional concept, but most definitions of it include aspects like the availability of seats and seating comfort, the evenness of the surface on which the vehicle moves, the temperature inside the vehicle, onboard services offered (food, entertainment), and information of expected time of arrival, etc. In fully autonomous vehicles, one relevant aspect of travel comfort is likely to be trust in the system – a

reassurance that it functions reliably and is resilient against cyberattacks. If people worry about such aspects, they may hesitate to use autonomous vehicles, no matter how comfortable the seats are. As travel comfort ultimately contains a large element of personal taste, and is thus to some extent subjective, it is best described by means of surveys in which people report their level of comfort according to predefined scales.

Vehicle ownership rates can be described as the percentage of individuals, or households, owning, 0, 1, 2, etc. cars (or other motor vehicles). Automation is likely to make individual car ownership less attractive. There are at least two reasons for this. First, quite a few people like to drive and dislike the idea of giving up the fun of driving. Unless automated vehicles are forced on people, the most passionate drivers are unlikely to buy such vehicles and will hold on to manual vehicles as long as possible. Ultimately, however, car manufacturers may stop making manual vehicles, if the market for them gets too small. Passionate drivers may then be forced to give up driving. Second, since automated vehicles are likely to be integrated into huge information systems, there will be less need for having a car waiting in the garage at any time. Information systems will enable booking cars when needed. Definite predictions are, however, impossible to make. One can only make conditional statements of the form IF (assumption), THEN (effect).

Shared mobility services include car sharing schemes, which are already established in many cities, but should be understood to also include new solutions for hiring cars or UBER-like taxi systems. It is widely assumed that car sharing will become more widespread when vehicles are automated and integrated into information systems keeping track of their availability. Car sharing will reduce the number of cars needed to provide a certain level of transport. In developing scenarios, estimation of potential impacts must once again rely on conditional if, then statements.

The main modes of transport are walking, cycling, driving a car and using public transport. The proliferation of connected and automated vehicles may influence the modal split of travel in an area. Through car sharing schemes, travel by car is likely to become cheaper. Since a shared car will often have more than one occupant, it resembles public transport. It will, however, differ from public transport in its current form by not running according to a time table, not running on specific routes, and generally using smaller vehicles than public transport. Public transport may itself become highly automated, which may increase its competitiveness. If vehicles are fully autonomous, a driver will not be needed and the cost of having a driver is saved. This can make it possible to increase frequency, which is a major quality factor in public transport. If there is a bus every third minute, you do not need to know the time table. Definite predictions remain impossible, but scenarios based on specific assumptions can be developed.

Cheaper transport in general stimulates it. Commuting longer distances may be felt as less burdensome if you do not have to drive, but can just sit back and relax or work. In general, city centres and nearby suburbs are well served by public transport. The further out you get, the more common is US-style suburbs with single family houses with gardens. This type of urban development has until now been difficult to serve well by means of public transport. Distances are often too long for walking or cycling. That leaves the car as the clearly best mode of travel for suburban dwellers. It is an increasingly common policy objective to reduce this car dependency. Automated vehicles may offer an opportunity for it, if, by means of advanced information systems, well-functioning car sharing schemes can be developed. Such systems will not be quite like public transport, but may at least enable 5-10 commuters to ride together for most the distance of their commutes.

Today, most cars rely on fossil fuels. Hybrid and electric cars are expanding rapidly and may soon have the same range as a fossil fuelled car on a full tank. Automation is expected

to increase fuel efficiency. If electric vehicles become common, energy efficiency can be greatly improved, and the operating cost of a vehicle reduced. Furthermore, emissions from the operation of vehicles will greatly diminish.

Finally, automated transport promises to make unassisted individual travel possible for groups that are now excluded from this, like children or those with functional impairments. It should be stressed, however, that this accessibility will only be feasible with fully autonomous vehicles, never needing driver intervention. It is clearly hazardous to allow children or impaired individuals, who perhaps have no experience as drivers, to ride in vehicles where driver intervention might be needed. A (small) child might not understand what to do, and a blind person or a wheelchair user might not be able to intervene.

4 Estimating impacts of connected and automated transport systems

This section discusses how impacts of connected and automated transport systems can be estimated in numerical terms. Each impact is discussed in turn, starting with impacts on safety. It will be assumed that the transport system subject to study is the road transport system. Other transport modes are not considered.

4.1 Safety

Connected and automated vehicles are widely expected to bring about large improvements in safety, but no standard approach has been developed for estimating these impacts. One may distinguish between the following main approaches:

1. Estimates based on findings of in-depth studies of accidents (The in-depth approach)
2. Estimated based on epidemiological studies of the contributions of risk factors to accident (The epidemiologic approach)
3. Estimates based on evaluations of specific technologies already on the market or close market launching (The system evaluation approach)
4. Estimates based on comparative analysis of the reliability of human operators and automated systems (The comparative reliability approach).
5. Estimates based on comparing the actual accident rates of automated vehicles to the accident rates of manual vehicles (The accident rate comparison approach)

The feasibility of each approach, especially when applied for forecasting and backcasting as part of a scenario is discussed below.

4.1.1 The in-depth approach

In-depth studies of accidents typically identify human error as a major contributor to accidents. Examples include lack of observation (caused by distractions), misunderstandings of situations (erroneously thinking that another road user would give way), and misjudgements (erroneously believing stopping distance was adequate). In-depth studies have been made in many countries. Some kind of human error is usually classified as having contributed to about 90 % of the accidents. As an example, in-depth studies of fatal accidents in Norway in 2017 (Ringen 2018), identified factors related to the road user as contributory in 93 % of the accidents. Based on this estimate, it is tempting to conclude

that by eliminating human drivers, one may eliminate all accidents to which human error contributed. For an example in the literature, see Fagnant and Kockelman (2015).

For a number of reasons, it is most likely incorrect to conclude that one can reduce accidents by 90 % by eliminating the contribution human error is judged to make to the accidents. In the first place, errors may be the result of complexities or deficiencies in the traffic environment. By improving the traffic environment, errors may become less likely, even if drivers continue to operate their vehicles just as before. In the second place, in-depth studies are often made of fatal accidents only. The driver will often be dead, and no information can be obtained from him or her. Concluding that an error was made is very much a call of judgement on the part of accident investigators. In the third place, in-depth studies adopt a very partial perspective by only studying severe accidents, not all the situations in which accidents were avoided because road users did the right thing. Accident rates, i.e. accidents per kilometre of travel, are remarkably low, suggesting that road users get it right most of the time and operate at a very high level of reliability.

Despite these reservations, it is clear that a detailed reconstruction of human errors may guide the development of technology designed to eliminate the errors. Forgetting to check the blind zone when changing lanes is a common error. Blind spot detection and warning systems (lane change assistant) may eliminate this error. However, such a straightforward linkage between problem (error) and solution (technology) is only possible when the error can be described in precise terms. Misinterpreting the behaviour of other road users in informal interactions is an error of a vague nature and difficult to replace by automation, as it relies on subtle signals like eye contact or body posture, which are challenging to encode in the software programs operating fully autonomous vehicles. The in-depth approach has serious limitations (it is mostly applied to fatal accidents only and the description of errors is often in quite general terms). It will therefore not be applied as the main approach for estimating safety effects, but can be applied to supplement other approaches at a detailed level of analysis as illustrated in the example above (lane change assistant).

4.1.2 The epidemiologic approach

Epidemiological studies aim to quantify the contribution of various risk factors to accidents and injuries, and the potential reduction of the number of accidents or injuries that can be attained by eliminating the increase in risk associated with a risk factor. The potential for reducing accidents or injuries is generally stated as attributable risk, which is defined as follows:

$$\text{Attributable risk} = \frac{PE(RR-1)}{(PE(RR-1))+1}$$

PE is the proportion of exposure (vehicle kilometres) exposed to a certain risk factor. RR is the relative risk associated with a risk factor. Thus, if 30 % of traffic is in darkness and the risk is 50 % higher than in daylight, PE = 0.30 and RR = 1.50. In a study of the prospects for improving road safety in Sweden, Elvik and Amundsen (2000) estimated attributable risk for about 20 risk factors. The results, taken from Elvik (2012) are reproduced in Table 2. The table shows first-order attributable risks, i.e. the attributable risk estimated for each risk factor without considering its correlation or interaction with other risk factors. It is seen that risk factors in each of the main groups identified all make a substantial contribution to fatalities and injuries.

To give an example of the interpretation of the estimates, consider poor car crashworthiness. The attributable risk for fatalities is estimated to 0.341. This means that if all cars had the best crashworthiness performance of cars in their weight class, the number

of fatalities could be reduced by 34 %. One of the attributable risks is negative (travel in an urban traffic environment). This means that it is a protective factor; in other words, the risk of fatal injury per kilometre travelled is lower in urban areas than in rural areas.

Attributable risks sum to more than 1, in fact to 2.36 for fatalities and 1.56 for injuries. This does obviously not mean that one can eliminate fatalities two times over. Of course, the potential reduction of fatalities or injuries that can be obtained by fully or partly eliminating the attributable risks cannot sum to more than 1. How come, then, that the attributable risks sum to more than 1?

It shows, basically, the same as in-depth studies, which is that more than one factor contributes to each accident. Thus, in the in-depth studies of fatal accidents in Norway in 2017, an average of 2.08 road user related factors were identified in each fatal accident; 0.29 vehicle related factors were identified; 0.45 road related factors and 0.18 environmental factors; in total 3.00 factors per fatal accident (Ringen 2018).

Table 2: First order attributable risk associated with various risk factors in Sweden. Based on Elvik and Amundsen (2000); reproduced from Elvik (2012)

Risk factor	Reference condition	First-order attributable risk	
		Fatal injuries	All injuries
A: System design			
A1: Travel in an urban traffic environment	Travel in a rural traffic environment	-0.131	0.214
A2: Substandard roads	Roads with good standard	0.034	0.010
A3: Unprotected roadside obstacles	Clear roadsides	0.167	0.039
A4: Erroneous highway signs	Correct highway signs	0.010	0.015
A5: High-risk junctions	Low-risk junctions	0.036	0.022
A6: Poor car crashworthiness	Best car crashworthiness in each weight class	0.341	0.066
A7: Involvement of heavy vehicles in crashes	No involvement of heavy vehicles in crashes	0.106	0.005
A. Total		0.563	0.371
B: Environmental Factors			
B1: Darkness	Daylight	0.165	0.107
B2: Winter and wet roads	Summer and dry roads	0.196	0.146
B3: Animals	No animals	0.015	0.038
B. Total		0.376	0.291
C: Vulnerability of road users			
C1: Unprotected road users	Protected road users (car occupants)	0.320	0.266
C2: Children	Adults	0.016	0.022
C3: Young drivers	Middle-aged drivers (safest age groups)	0.086	0.101
C4: Older road users	Middle-aged road users (safest age groups)	0.206	0.068
C. Total		0.628	0.457
D: Unsafe road user behavior			
D1: Speeding	Keeping speed limits	0.376	0.210
D2: Drinking and driving	Driver sober	0.072	0.048
D3: Not wearing seat belts	Wearing seat belts	0.084	0.032
D4: Other violations	No violations	0.092	0.061
D5: Excessive driving in towns	No excessive driving in towns	0.005	0.015
D. Total		0.629	0.366
E: Rescue services			
E1: Not state-of-the-art rescue service	State-of-the-art rescue services	0.167	0.071
E. Total		0.167	0.071
F: Total of all risk factors		2.363	1.556

It is reasonable to expect fully automated and autonomous vehicles to eliminate or greatly reduce most of the attributable risks listed in Table 2. Age and other characteristics of the driver – which are major risk factors today – would no longer matter if the vehicle is

driverless. They might continue to matter if automation was partial only and the driver would be asked to take control in certain situations.

Unfortunately, it is not easy to estimate the combined effects of eliminating all or most of the risk factors listed in Table 2. The principal problem is that many of the risk factors are highly correlated. Eliminating the contribution of one of a pair of highly correlated risk factors would then go some way towards eliminating the contribution of the other. Unless correlations among the risk factors are accounted for, there may be serious double counting of potential benefits of eliminating the risk factors.

At this point, limits of current knowledge impose a serious restriction on the epidemiological approach. Elvik and Amundsen (2000) tried to account for correlations among the risk factors. It would detract from the main purpose of this paper to go into details about how this was done. It did, however, reduce the sum of attributable risks from 2.56 to 1.96 for fatalities and from 1.56 to 1.23 for injuries. The combined effect of eliminating all attributable risks, adjusted for overlap and correlations between them, was estimated by using the method of common residuals. The basic logic of this method can be explained as follows:

Suppose the risk attributable to factor A is 0.2 and the risk attributable to factor B is 0.1. The combined effect of eliminating the risk factors is then not 0.3 – the sum of their attributable risks. If risk factor A is eliminated, it leaves a residual of 0.8 ($1 - 0.2$). Eliminating risk factor B can only act on the residual, i.e. it reduces risk by 0.1 of 0.8, or 0.08. The combined contribution is then 0.28.

By applying the method of common residuals, one ensures that the total reduction of fatalities and injuries resulting from the combined elimination of a set of attributable risks can never exceed the value of 1. It is mathematically impossible, as indeed it should be. Elvik and Amundsen (2000) estimated that by eliminating all risk factors listed in Table 2, fatalities could be reduced by 89 % and injuries by 73 %. Elvik (2009) subsequently developed a more conservative version of the method of common residuals, the dominant common residuals method, which tries to account for correlations among risk factors.

The epidemiological approach is flexible, as it can be used both to estimate potential effects of full automation and potential effects of partial automation, depending on the risk factors included in the estimation. Ideally speaking, estimates of attributable risk should be customised to each use case. This will almost surely not be possible for all risk factors listed in Table 2. Nevertheless, educated guesses can be made about the magnitude of attributable risks. It is inevitable to rely on educated guesses to some extent, since no definite predictions of the impacts of connected and automated vehicles is possible, only conditional predictions of the form: if assumption, then effect. It then matters less if the assumption is strictly correct, although it should of course be as consistent with established knowledge as possible.

Another useful aspect of the epidemiological approach is that it can be used to identify those accidents or injuries that do not easily, or not at all, lend themselves to automation. This can be done by classifying accidents or injuries according to parties involved. Table 3 shows an example of this, based on a paper by Elvik (2008).

Table 3: Injuries by combinations of parties involved in injury accidents in Norway 1998-2005. Based on Elvik (2008).

Injured as occupant of	Counterpart in accident													Total
	Truck-trailer	Truck	Bus	Van	Car	Large MC	Small MC	Moped	Cycle	Pedestrian	Other	None		
Truck-trailer	73	32	10	5	96	0	1	0	2	0	3	533	755	
Truck	80	102	37	40	197	3	0	2	2	1	22	481	967	
Bus	120	103	63	43	290	1	0	7	3	8	36	627	1,301	
Van	115	214	80	271	1,038	3	0	4	3	8	35	954	2,725	
Car	1789	2736	1210	2815	31,355	203	31	59	59	78	543	19,859	60,737	
Large MC	41	84	46	128	1,926	107	5	26	25	25	43	2,216	4,672	
Small MC	10	14	9	47	474	4	14	21	6	5	10	340	954	
Moped	23	68	47	150	2,350	17	26	139	36	51	46	1,036	3,989	
Cycle	42	144	105	286	4,388	42	12	82	254	58	83	644	6,140	
Pedestrian	54	220	318	409	5,635	61	13	147	167	37	188	185	7,434	
Other	17	54	14	20	158	5	0	2	4	2	31	414	721	
Total	2364	3771	1939	4214	47,907	446	102	489	561	273	1040	27,289	90,395	

One may identify the following groups of road users or vehicles as unlikely to become automated:

1. Pedestrians
2. Bicyclists
3. Moped riders
4. Motorcycle riders (in table 3, a distinction is made between large and small motorcycles)
5. Operators of road works machines (other in Table 3)
6. Operators of agricultural tractors (other in Table 3)

These groups will continue to have single accidents or collisions between themselves even after full automation of all other vehicles. Injuries in these types of accidents are highlighted in yellow in Table 3 and located inside the rectangle indicated. There are 6629 injuries in total, making up a little more than 7 % of the total. If the assumption, based on Elvik and Amundsen (2000), is made that the maximum potential for reducing the remaining injuries is 73 %, a maximum total reduction of injuries of 67.5 % can be estimated. This estimate should be adjusted further downwards to account for unreliability of first generation automation technology and the risk of cyberattacks. There is no knowledge to permit a precise adjustment for these factors. Once more, it is necessary to rely on educated guesses.

4.1.3 The system evaluation approach

The third approach to estimating the safety effects of connected and automated vehicles is to estimate effects of systems already on the market or close to being launched on the market. An example of this kind of estimation is given in a paper by Yue et al. (2018). They evaluated the effects of the following driver assistance systems:

1. Forward collision warning (a system labelled collision warning is also listed; it is not clear what the difference between this system and forward collision warning is)
2. Autonomous emergency braking (a system called autobrake is also listed)
3. Adaptive cruise control
4. Collision mitigation brake system
5. Pedestrian crash avoidance and mitigation system
6. Blind spot warning
7. Lane change warning
8. Intersection movement assist
9. Left turn assist

10. Lane departure warning
11. Electronic stability control
12. Backup collision intervention (warning when reversing close to an object)
13. Rearview cameras

Many of these systems have been on the market for some time and their effects have been evaluated. Yue et al. (2018) evaluate the combined effects of all systems, based on a review of evaluation studies. They conclude that for light vehicles, the best estimate of the total effect is 33 % accident reduction when all vehicles have all the systems. This estimate applies to all accidents, the large majority of which are property-damage-only accidents. Estimates were not specified according to accident severity.

For trucks, the safety systems were estimated to reduce accidents by 41 % when all vehicles have all systems. In the transition period, before all systems reach full market penetration, safety effects will be smaller, but gradually increase to reach the maximum value at full penetration of all systems. The systems evaluated by Yue et al. (2018) are all driver assistance systems, representing level 1 automation according to the SAE typology. The driver remains in control of the vehicle, but the systems provide information, give warnings, or reinforce driver action (braking harder) in order to assist the driver.

4.1.4 The comparative reliability approach

The fourth approach to evaluating the potential effects of connected and automated vehicles was called the comparative reliability approach. A paper by Noy, Shinar and Horrey (2018) touches on this approach and provide the basis for outlining its basic elements. One starting point is that human operators in the transport system are very reliable. Accident rate per kilometre of travel is very low; if accidents are taken as evidence of errors or mistakes made by road users, the rate of errors or mistakes is extremely low, or the system is extremely forgiving of errors or mistakes.

Technology designed to replace human operators must have at least the same level of reliability as human operators; otherwise it will not improve safety. To take a very simple example: Most of the time, drivers are able to adapt their speed to the vehicle in front of them. Most cases of braking do not end in a rear-end collision. While the exact “success rate” in avoiding rear-end collisions is unknown, let us assume it is 999,999 out of 1,000,000. This rate of reliability is the minimum a technical replacement of a human must attain in order to improve safety. It such a level of reliability possible?

Braking is not just braking. Situations vary. An experienced driver will be capable of adjusting behaviour to a slippery road surface and to going downhill. Will technology be able to adjust similarly? Besides, if a driver realises he will not be able to stop in time, he may sometimes be able to swerve into a safe space and still avoid a collision. Will technology have the same level of sophistication?

These are admittedly rhetorical questions. Yet, they are relevant and demand answers. The problem is that both the reliability of human operators and of technology are too poorly known to quantify it and determine any differences in reliability. Besides, human reliability is not constant; it cannot be represented by a single number. It will be greatly reduced if, for example, the driver is influenced by alcohol.

Probably the most detailed and representative data that can shed light on human reliability are data from naturalistic driving studies. Dingus et al. (2016) provide data based on the SHRP 2 naturalistic driving study. As of April 2015 (which was probably when the paper was written) these data represented more than 56 million kilometres of driving, during which more than 1,500 accidents had happened. Since all events are continuously

monitored, it is reasonable to assume that accident data are complete. Mean accident rate was 26.8 per million kilometres driven, corresponding to a reliability level per kilometre driven of 0.9999732 (i.e. the probability that a randomly selected kilometre was accident free). Table 4 reproduces estimates of risk based on the study.

Table 4: Risks associated with driver distraction and errors. Taken from Dingus et al. 2016

	O.R. (95% CI)	Baseline Prevalence
Observable Impairment*		
Overall	5.2 (3.8 - 7.1)	1.92%
Drug/alcohol	35.9 (17.0 - 75.8)	0.08%
Drowsiness/fatigue	3.4 (2.3 - 5.1)	1.57%
Emotion (anger, sadness, crying, and/or emotional agitation)	9.8 (5.0 - 19.0)	0.22%
Driver Performance Error		
Overall	18.2 (14.8 - 22.3)	4.81%
Major error sub-categories (observed in crash and baseline events)		
Apparent inexperience with vehicle/roadway	204.5 (111.1 - 376.6)	0.07%
Blind spot error	55.1 (21.6 - 140.6)	0.05%
Improper turn	92.1 (68.8 - 123.4)	0.51%
Right-of-way error	936.1 (123.8 - 7078.3)	0.01%
Signal violation	28.3 (15.9 - 50.2)	0.19%
Stop/yield sign violation	7.4 (4.9 - 11.4)	1.05%
Wrong side of road	22.3 (12.0 - 41.5)	0.19%
Driving too slowly	2.3 (1.1 - 4.8)	0.97%
Sudden or improper braking/stopping	247.8 (53.1 - 1156.2)	0.01%
Failed to signal	2.5 (1.5 - 4.0)	2.27%
Driver Momentary Judgment Error (Speeding/Aggressive Driving)		
Overall	11.1 (9.0 - 13.8)	4.22%
Aggressive driving (general observed behavior)	34.8 (17.2 - 70.5)	0.10%
Speeding (over limit and too fast for conditions)	12.8 (10.1 - 16.2)	2.77%
Speeding/unsafe in work zone	14.2 (3.9 - 52.0)	0.05%
Illegal/unsafe passing	14.4 (7.2 - 28.8)	0.18%
Following too closely	13.5 (4.4 - 41.4)	0.07%
Intentional signal violation	15.3 (7.9 - 29.9)	0.19%
Intentional stop/yield sign violation	5.3 (3.4 - 8.4)	1.04%
Observable Distraction**		
Overall	2.0 (1.8 - 2.4)	51.93%
Major distraction sub-categories (observed in crash and baseline events)		
In-vehicle radio	1.9 (1.2 - 3.0)	2.21%
In-vehicle climate control	2.3 (1.1 - 5.0)	0.56%
In-vehicle device (other)	4.6 (2.9 - 7.4)	0.83%
Total in-vehicle device	2.5 (1.8 - 3.4)	3.53%
Cell browse	2.7 (1.5 - 5.1)	0.73%
Cell dial (handheld)	12.2 (5.6 - 26.4)	0.14%
Cell reach	4.8 (2.7 - 8.4)	0.58%
Cell text (handheld)	6.1 (4.5 - 8.2)	1.91%
Cell talk (handheld)	2.2 (1.6 - 3.1)	3.24%
Total cell (handheld)	3.6 (2.9 - 4.5)	6.40%
Child rear seat	0.5 (0.1 - 1.9)	0.80%
Interaction with adult/teen passenger	1.4 (1.1 - 1.8)	14.58%
Reading/writing (includes tablet)	9.9 (3.6 - 26.9)	0.09%
Eating	1.8 (1.1 - 2.9)	1.90%
Drinking (non-alcohol)	1.8 (1.0 - 3.3)	1.22%
Personal hygiene	1.4 (0.8 - 2.5)	1.69%
Reaching for object (non-cell phone)	9.1 (6.5 - 12.6)	1.08%
Dancing in seat to music	1.0 (0.4 - 2.3)	1.10%
Extended glance duration to external object	7.1 (4.8 - 10.4)	0.93%

Dingus et al. (2016) note that at least one error was present in 87.7 % of the accidents, a value close to the 90 % typically reported by in-depth studies. A distinction was made between distractions, errors and impairments. Distractions were found in 68.3 % of accidents, errors in 73.7 % and impairments in 6.4 % of accidents. These percentages sum to more than 100, since more than one factor was found in many accidents.

Based on Table 4, the sum of attributable risks for the main groups listed can be estimated to 1.168. Clearly, accidents cannot be reduced by 116.8 %. However, applying the common residuals method, the effect of eliminating all risk factors was estimated to an accident reduction of 76.6 %, which is quite close to the value found based on Table 2 (the risk factors for Sweden), but still significantly lower than the more than 90 % accident reduction some have assumed based on in-depth studies.

4.1.5 The accident rate comparison approach

Noy, Shinar and Horrey (2018) mention studies that have found automated cars to have higher accident rates (accidents per million kilometres driven) than manually driven cars. These studies are based on very few accidents and must therefore be regarded as inconclusive. A considerable amount of data is needed in order to reliably estimate any difference in safety between manual and automated cars (Kalra and Paddock 2016). At present there are far too few automated vehicles operating on public roads to meaningfully compare their accident rates to those of manual cars.

This does not mean that one cannot benefit from in-depth studies of accidents involving automated cars. There have already been a few accidents that suggest areas for improving the functioning of sensors and the detection and interpretation of the behaviour of other road users to reduce the likelihood of accidents. Current technology for automated cars is not a mature technology; it is a first-generation technology which has not benefitted from all opportunities for learning and improving functioning that use of the technology in the real world affords.

Comparing accident rates for manual and automated cars is currently not a feasible approach for quantifying the safety impacts of automated cars.

4.1.6 How to predict safety impacts – preliminary recommendations

The epidemiologic approach, based on data from naturalistic driving studies, appears to provide the most detailed and flexible approach to the prediction of the safety impacts of connected and automated vehicles. To apply the method, one should at the first stage classify accidents to identify those that will not benefit from vehicle automation. These accidents made up 7 % of all injury accidents in Norway (or, more precisely, 7 % of injured road users), but the share will vary from country to country. Next, for those accidents that can benefit from automation, the following approximate relationship between the penetration of automation technology and changes in the number of accidents can be assumed:

Short term (5 years ahead): greater market penetration of advanced driver assistance systems: 15-20 % accident reduction.

Medium term (10-15 years): full market penetration of advanced driver assistance systems; some use of technology for connected driving: 30-40 % accident reduction.

Long term (25+ years): all vehicles are fully automated, but technology still only matches the highest levels of human reliability in manual driving; risk and impacts of cyberattacks are unknown: 65-75 % accident reduction.

The point estimate of eliminating the risks attributable to all the risk factors identified for Sweden was 73 %; the point estimate based on the SHRP 2 naturalistic driving study was close to 77 %. To allow for imperfect technology and cyberattacks, these estimates are adjusted down to 70 %, with an uncertainty margin of plus or minus five percentage points.

4.2 Road capacity

Connected and automated vehicles are expected to utilise road capacity more efficiently than manually driven vehicles, principally by being more closely spaced and by keeping the same speed. A better utilisation of road capacity will, all else equal, reduce congestion and thus reduce travel time. Effects of reducing space between vehicles and eliminating speed variation can be simulated. For the moment, some studies that have tried to quantify impacts will be quoted.

Fernandes and Nunes (2012) estimate an increase in lane capacity of up to 175 % at a speed of 36 km/h for platoons of vehicles consisting of up to 20 vehicles per platoon, spaced by only 1 metre. Each vehicle was assumed to be 3 metres long, which is shorter than virtually all cars found in traffic today. It is likely that the potential increase in capacity would be smaller if there is a mix of vehicles of different lengths. At a speed of 72 km/h, the maximum potential increase in lane capacity was estimated to be 370 %, meaning that capacity increase almost by a factor of five. Again, the small dimensions assumed for the vehicles makes this overly optimistic.

Fagnant and Kockelman (2015) quote a study estimating potential impacts of cooperative adaptive cruise control, a system resembling connected driving. Lane capacity was estimated to increase by 1 % at 10 % market penetration of the system, by 21 % at 50 % market penetration and by 80 % at 90 % market penetration.

Milakis, van Arem and van Wee (2017) quote various studies that indicate that capacity could be more than doubled by full penetration of technology for connected driving. Meyer et al. (2018) perform an analysis for Switzerland assuming (main alternative) 80 % capacity increase for inter-urban roads (at full penetration of automated vehicles), with 270 % increase assumed in a sensitivity analysis. For urban roads, a capacity increase of 40 % was assumed.

It seems clear that connected and automated driving has a potential for substantially increasing road capacity. Exactly how large the increase can be, depends on the assumptions made regarding vehicle dimensions, driving speed, length of platoons, distance between vehicles within a platoon and distance between platoons. Fernandes and Nunes give the following formula for road capacity (lane capacity) taking account of these factors:

$$C = v \frac{n}{ns + (n-1)d + D}$$

C is capacity, indicated as vehicles passing per second (to obtain hourly volume, multiply by 3,600), n is the number of connected cars in each platoon (1 if cars drive independently and are not platooned), s is vehicle length in metres (it can be the average value of vehicles differing in length), v is speed in metres per second, d is intraplatoon spacing in metres, and D is spacing between platoons in metres. When applying the formula, it can be assumed that fully automated vehicles have the capacity to be connected and form platoons. However, vehicles can have technology for driving connected without being automated.

To give an example, assume that no vehicles are connected ($n = 1$), that they drive at 40 km/h (11.1 metres per second), that mean length is 6 metres, and that mean time headway is 2 seconds (equal to 22.2 metres). The factor d drops out (is set to zero), whereas D represents headway. We get:

$$C = 11.1 \frac{1}{1 \cdot 6 + 0 + 22.2} = 0.3936$$

This corresponds to an hourly capacity of 1417 ($0.3936 \cdot 3600$). Now assume that vehicles are connected in platoons each consisting of 15 cars ($n = 15$). The spacing of cars within each platoon is 2 metres ($d = 2$). The spacing between platoons is 55.6 metres (5 seconds), allowing pedestrians to use the gap between two platoons to cross the road. We now get:

$$C = 11.1 \frac{15}{15 \cdot 6 + 14 \cdot 2 + 55.6} = 0.9591$$

This corresponds to an hourly capacity of 3452 vehicles. By varying the assumptions made, it is possible to estimate changes in capacity for different speeds, different vehicle lengths, different lengths of platoons, different spacing within platoons and different spacing between platoons. Thus, the framework provided by Fernandes and Nunes (2012) is very flexible, although the assumptions they make in applying it seem to be overly optimistic.

4.3 Effects on infrastructure wear due to traffic loading

The benefits of increased road capacity due to automated driving lead to the questions of effects on infrastructure wear. The above example illustrates quite well that shortening of the headway distances leads to higher vehicle numbers on road sections. The primary effect on infrastructure wear is expected due to more concentrated loads of heavy vehicles in combination with automated driving. Especially the formation of uniformed truck platoons, which should reduce the fuel consumption by using positive aerodynamic effects, will lead to an increased loading of roads and bridges compared to a single vehicle entity. On the contrary, change of number of passenger cars on sections will have minor effects on infrastructure loading. Secondary effects of automated driving are expected to manifest in changed traffic flows and possibly modified dynamic amplification of axle loads on bridges.

Most impacts of changed loading are expected to concern bridges. The standards for designing are regulated by the *European Committee for Standardization (CEN)*, which covers almost all member countries within the European Union. There is a master code with the main regulations, each member state has his own national annex for covering regional requirements. The load models are regulated in the Eurocode 1991-2 “*Traffic loads on Bridges*”. This code defines the characteristic load model for dimensioning new main bridges. The so-called Load Model 1 (LM1) is based on a 1000-year return period of traffic loads (based on a reference in 2003) which is equal to a probability of exceedance of 5% in 50 years for traffic on the main roads in Europe (Calgaro 2008). This enables to fulfill the structural safety regulations of the CEN Standards which should cover the design life of 100 -120 years or more. This restriction is predominantly used for the design of new bridges. For assessment of existing bridges, the remaining service life is generally less than the design life and it may be more appropriate to use a shorter return period of traffic events, which is equivalent to a lower level of safety (Leahy C 2016). There are different approaches for assessment of existing bridges. Leahy C 2016 suggested a return period of 75 years (as it is used in bridge design in the United States).

Another aspect is the change of load patterns due to automated traffic. Stochastic traffic produces random forces, while automated driving or truck platoons lead to synchronised traffic flows with synchronised loading. Synchronization will change the dynamic interaction or can increase the horizontal loading, for example in case of an emergency brake performed by the whole truck platoon. It will be necessary to identify the changed load impacts as consequence of the truck platoon configuration and to investigate their effects on infrastructure components. For example, bridges with smaller spans (< 30 m) are more sensitive to dynamic interactions, while longer bridges will be more restricted by

the maximum number of trucks on the bridge. Steel bridges with low dynamic damping factor behave differently than concrete bridges.

The most **relevant load impacts** are expected on bridges, which will be:

- a) Vertical loading
- b) Horizontal loading
- c) Dynamic interaction

Ad a) It is obvious that increasing the number of trucks/per h or shortening the headway distances leads to a more trucks per section which changes the infrastructure loading. The effects of **vertical loading** are mainly dependent on the vehicle weight, the bridge span and platoon length/headways and must meet the bridge design restrictions.

	3,40	70
	6,00	140
	1,80	90
		90

Axle spacing[m] Axle weight [kN]

Example of an equivalent trailer truck according to EN 1991-2 (Calgaro 2008).

The change of load can be demonstrated in the following example: A truck platoon consisting of 8 trucks, with average truck load of 39 to (390 kN) and a single truck length of 14 m, is passing with a speed of 80 km/h over a bridge with a length of 128 m. Using a common mean time headway of 2 seconds (44.4 m) results to a total bridge loading of 2.19 trucks or 85 to. Reducing the distance between the vehicles to 2 m, the whole platoon will fit with its 8 trucks or 312 to on the bridge, which is an additional loading of + 267 %.

Other restrictions of increased loading could arise from torsional effects due to different loading in individual lanes, or due to local effects corresponding to transverse bearing capacity.

Ad b) The change of **horizontal loading** is mainly expected as the change of breaking loads due to abrupt breaking of a whole truck platoon on a bridge. According to EN 1991-2 new bridges are designed to a horizontal load which is depending on the total bridge length (Calgaro 2008):

$$Q_{lk} = 360kN + 2,7 L < 900 kN \quad \text{for } 1,2m < L < 200 m$$

For bridge with 1,2 m length the horizontal load Q_{lk} due to breaking of LM1 would be 363 kN and rises to a maximum of 900 kN for bridges with 200 m length.

The effects can be illustrated using the above truck platoon with 8 trucks, which performs an emergency break with deceleration of 6 m/sec² (dry asphalt) on a bridge with length L=128 m. Applying Newton's law, the acting horizontal force of the platoon is:

$$Q_{lk p} = m * a_b = 8 * 39000 kg * 6 ms^{-2} = 1.872 kN$$

This is far more than the Eurocode load, which would be only 706 kN. It cannot be guaranteed that existing bridges are designed for that level of horizontal forces.

Other effects of horizontal loads are centrifugal loads or accidental loads of single straying trucks. Here also, some changes can be expected due to platooning.

Ad c) **Dynamic effects** are mostly observed when the traffic flow changes from random to more synchronized forms. The changed dynamic amplification and possibly increased

resonance loading effects, which are well-known from railway bridges, could now act also on existing road bridges, which were not designed for that.

In general, the dynamic effect of traffic loads is determined by many factors, such as maximal bridge span length, bridge natural frequency, vehicle weight, axle loads, axle configuration, vehicle suspension properties, current vehicle position on the bridge, quality of pavement, and stiffness of structural members. However, a large contribution may be attributed to vibrations of the vehicle induced by the road profile roughness, depending on the velocity and road surface unevenness (Cantieni 1992, Prat 2001). Changed fatigue consumption of bridges and their components due to synchronised loading could affect the expected bridge lifetime.

4.4 The effects of changed loading due automatisation and truck platooning must go along with existing bridges and detailed investigation of different bridge types and truck platoons are needed for assessment of these effects. Bhoopalam et al, 2018 stated that measures to fulfill the infrastructure needs could lead to restrictions on maximum weight or smart division of truck loads, or decoupling of truck platoons at bridges. Other measures could be temporary changes in the truck platoon speed or changes of headway distances, so that the bridge loads would not exceed the original design levels. Another option would be legal limitations on the total number of trucks in a platoon, as demonstrated in the lessons learnt of European truck platooning challenge (Eckhardt et al., 2016). Travel time

Changes in travel time for trips with given origins and destinations as a result of connected or automated driving will be the result of a number of other changes:

1. Changes in traffic volume: the most common prediction is that traffic volume will increase, in particular because fully automated transport will reduce the generalised costs of travel,
2. Changes in the utilisation of road capacity: if connected or automated vehicles can utilise road capacity more effectively, a higher volume can be served before delays in travel time arise,
3. Changes in driving speed: it is reasonable to assume that connected or automated vehicles will be programmed to comply with speed limits; if these remain unchanged, there will be a small increase in travel time as a result of the elimination of speeding,
4. Changes in route choice: if connected and automated vehicles have access to real-time data on travel delays on different routes, routes that minimise travel time for given trips may be chosen; to the extent current route choices are suboptimal, this may reduce travel time.

It is not known whether current volume-delay functions apply to connected and automated vehicles (Meyer et al. 2018). Although, as discussed above, road capacity may increase, there will be limits to how densely vehicles can be spaced within a platoon and to the lengths of platoons. Thus, even if road capacity increases, it will have a limit. When volume approaches the capacity limit, it seems reasonable to expect speed to be reduced even if

vehicles are connected or automated. There will be entering and leaving vehicles. These vehicle movements will at least result in minor perturbations in speed, particularly if the entering or leaving vehicles are located in the middle of a platoon, and not at the front or rear end of it. Thus, in the numerical example above, vehicles in a platoon of 15 vehicles may not be able to keep a constant speed of 40 km/h, as assumed in calculating road capacity. There must be gaps in platoons, or a facility for disconnecting from them, in order to change lanes, leave the highway or enter it from another road. These vehicle movements will cause speed variation and will reduce capacity from the theoretical maximum assumed above.

In short, it is difficult to imagine that fully automated transport can eliminate congestion. Traffic tends to fill up available capacity (Downs 1962). Road pricing may be introduced to reduce congestion; yet, it is not optimal to set prices so high that congestion is fully eliminated. Besides, very high prices will meet the objection of turning travel into a privilege of the rich and creating social exclusion in travel opportunities.

It is envisaged that traffic simulation will be performed and provide data on changes in travel time. At the current state of knowledge, it is impossible to make definite predictions. Any use case should, however, systematically collect data on travel time, preferably in a way permitting comparison to current travel times.

4.5 Geographic accessibility

Meyer et al. (2018) show that full implementation of automated driving can change the accessibility of locations, mostly by making them more accessible (i.e. possible to reach in a shorter time). To assess changes in accessibility, a transport model is needed. The model can then be run with current travel times and with new travel times applying to a fully automated transport system. Comparing the results will show changes in travel time to and from specific locations, thus indicating changes in accessibility.

It is not clear whether the use cases developed in Levitate need to address this potential impact of connected and automated transport systems.

4.6 Vehicle kilometres of travel

The most common prediction is that connected and automated transport will increase vehicle kilometres of travel. This is the expected result of increased travel induced by lower generalised costs of travel.

Preliminary estimates of changes in the generalised costs of travel can be found in the literature (Bösch et al. 2018, Fagnant and Kockelman 2015, Herrmann et al. 2018, Kolarova et al. 2018, Wadud 2017). These estimates differ with respect to the cost items included, and the impacts connected and automated transport are assumed to have on each cost item. While there is probably a high level of agreement on the definition of generalised costs of travel, there is no consensus about the likely impacts of connected and automated transport on these costs. A careful reading of the studies quoted above can perhaps serve as a basis for selecting reasonable best estimates as well as upper and lower estimates for use in sensitivity analysis.

To generalise the results, changes in cost should be stated in percentage terms, not in terms of the currencies used in the studies. Stating changes in the generalised costs of travel as percentage changes permits linking these changes directly to estimates of the elasticity of vehicle kilometres of travel with respect to the generalised costs of travel. An elasticity

shows the percent change in a response variable as a result of the percent change in an independent variable.

Estimates of the elasticity of vehicle kilometres of travel with respect to the generalised costs of travel are widely available and have been summarised by, for example, Litman (2017).

4.7 Optimisation of route choice

One potential impact of the information technology expected to be part of connected and automated driving, is the possibility of dynamically optimising route choice, based on real-time information about travel times on alternative routes. For there to be any benefit of this, however, current route choices must to some extent be suboptimal. If route choices are already optimal, there is no need for change and no gain can be realised.

To determine whether route choices are optimal or not, fairly detailed information is needed. Transport models normally assume that route choice is optimal. A transport model cannot be solved unless it relies on some kind of global equilibrium assumption, i.e. an assumption that no road user can save generalised costs of travel by choosing a different route, a different mode, or a different departure time. These assumptions are needed for computational reasons; it is widely understood that they may not be strictly correct.

It is well-known that choices of route, mode or time of travel rely on mental heuristics that are likely to result in sub-optimisation. Thus, Simon (1959) described what he called event matching. Suppose that, in the long run, taking the car will get you fastest to work 70 % of the time; taking the bus will be fastest 30 % of the time. What should a rational individual do? Always go by car. That will be the best choice 70 % of the time, which is the best that can be attained.

What is observed in practice is that individuals often try to mimic the relative frequencies with which the modes of transport are quickest. This is referred to as event matching. After a bad day of congestion, you try the bus the next day, only to find that it has a mechanical breakdown that delays you considerably. Ergo, back to the car the next day. And so on. In the long run, most people form stable travel habits. If the car really is the fastest 70 % of the time, most people will, by repeated trial, discover this and settle for always using the car. Objectively, however, that will be the fastest only 70 % of the time.

Nevertheless, an information system providing real-time data on travel times will not be able to always guide travellers to the optimal choice. If the car was the best choice in the morning, an accident may create long delays in the afternoon that the system could not foresee in the morning. Even if guided to a different route than the usual one, that route is likely to be more congested than usual, involving a longer travel time than usual.

Optimising departure time is an even more complex problem (Levinson 2005, Elvik 2014). This is essentially a co-ordination game without a solution, since individual preferences imply counterfinality in choices, i.e. if everybody acts in order to bring about their most preferred outcome, they will actually bring about their least preferred outcome.

Another aspect is the system-awareness of the route choices. In case optimised route suggestions to multiple simultaneously traveling users are made, they are usually not connected with each other, meaning that each user request is handled separately. Assume that the users have similar origin and destinations, it is likely that they will concurrently follow the same routes in a street network. Therefore, it is most likely that traffic congestion will occur. If the same set of travellers is, however, distributed over multiple roads/routes, the traffic flow is maintained, and negative effects are reduced. With the

introduction of CATS, new possibilities with respect to system-aware optimisation will arise.

4.8 Vehicle ownership cost

Vehicle ownership cost consist of the cost of buying a car and fixed costs of owning the car that do not depend on driving distance. An example a fixed cost is rent for a garage or an annual lump sum tax on cars. In estimates of the cost of car ownership, the price of the car is usually converted to an annual depreciation factor, reflecting the loss of value as the car ages.

Fully automated cars are expected to be more expensive (to buy) than current cars. A few cost estimates are found in the literature, e.g. Wadud (2017) and Bösch et al. (2018). A synthesis of these studies might provide a basis for general estimates of changes in vehicle ownership costs.

4.9 Vehicle operating cost

Vehicle operating cost refers to all costs that are incurred when operating a vehicle. The most obvious item is fuel, but it also includes items like tyre wear, washing the car, replacing worn window vipers, etc. Vehicle operating cost is usually stated per kilometre of driving. To obtain total costs, the fixed costs of car ownership are added to the operating costs.

Automated cars are generally believed to have lower operating costs than current cars, in particular if they are electric. The studies quoted above (Bösch et al. 2018, Fagnant and Kockelman 2015, Herrmann et al. 2018, Kolarova et al. 2018, Wadud 2017) contain estimates of vehicle operating costs for current and automated cars. A synthesis of these studies may provide a basis for general estimates of the changes to be expected when all cars are fully automated.

4.10 Use and valuation of travel time

Time spent as a driver has low value, because the time cannot be spent on much else. Hence, travel time savings are highly valued. When cars are fully automated, occupants may be able to spend time on other activities. This is believed to reduce the value of travel time savings.

A study by Kolarova et al. (2018) indicates that the value of saving time is roughly 45-55 % lower for a private automated car than for a manually operated car. For driverless taxi, the value of time savings was 10-30 % lower than for a privately owned manually operated car. These estimates are obviously highly preliminary, but do support the hypothesis of a lower valuation of time.

Travel time savings normally constitute the largest part of the benefits of road investments. All else equal, road investments may therefore become less attractive when all cars are fully automated.

4.11 Travel comfort

There is likely to be an interaction between travel comfort and the valuation of time for automated cars. It is not pleasant, of perhaps not even possible, to spend time reading or working if the road is very bumpy or if driving is very jerky. A smooth road surface and

gentle accelerations and decelerations are necessary to make it pleasant and attractive to spend onboard time on activities not related to travel.

While there is wide agreement that jerks and bumps are unpleasant, the concept of travel comfort contains a large subjective element. Some people will find even barely audible engine noise irritating; others will ignore it or not even notice it. Preferences also vary regarding, for example, the ideal temperature in a vehicle. Some like conversations when travelling; others prefer silence. In small vehicles, it may be difficult to cater to all preferences. Larger vehicles, long-distance trains for example, may have a “silent car” for those who prefer silence, a dining car for meals, or even, as found in Norway, a compartment where children can play.

Changes in travel comfort associated with a transition to automated vehicles are probably best captured by questionnaire surveys. These will need to be customised to specific use cases. Relevant aspects of comfort are not the same for urban shuttle buses as for private cars.

4.12 Vehicle ownership rates

One of the biggest advantages of owning a car, is that it is always available and always nearby. Accessing the cars involves a minimum of travel time, except perhaps when scarcity of parking space forces the owner to park some distance from the final destination. Currently, no other mode of transport, except walking and cycling, offers the same flexibility and all-time availability as individually owned cars. However, if connected and automated transport systems are integrated with real-time information systems, delays in getting transport can be minimised, and may perhaps be viewed as acceptable if the costs of travel are reduced. It is not possible to make definite predictions about car ownership rates. Analysis will therefore have to rely on non-verifiable assumptions about changes in car ownership rates.

It is noteworthy that one paper (Fagnant and Kockelman 2014) found that one shared autonomous vehicle can replace eleven conventional vehicles. This is possible because the shared vehicle will be operating much longer than the time an individually owned car is typically driven today, which is about one hour per day. Automation facilitates a much more efficient use of vehicles than the current individualised transport system allows for.

4.13 Use of shared mobility services

Car sharing schemes have been introduced in many cities and are slowly becoming more popular. Yet, the share of kilometres driven by cars belonging to car sharing schemes is still insignificant compared to kilometres driven in individually owned cars, perhaps in the order of 0.1 percent.

A Danish study (Kristensen et al. 2018) is reluctant in predicting that car sharing schemes can replace individual car ownership on a large scale. New business models may change this, but definite predictions are impossible to make. Payments for shared vehicles make the variable costs of driving more visible and thus seemingly higher than for privately owned cars. A widespread use of road pricing may change this, but it is uncertain if this will be introduced.

Given the many uncertainties, the only analysis possible at the moment is a conditional one: given this or that level of car sharing, what will be the impacts. The principal pathway for impacts is vehicle kilometres driven. Car owners who sell their car and rely on shared mobility only are likely to reduce their amount of driving. Users who never owned a car

may increase their driving when joining a car sharing scheme. Shared mobility is likely to have two main effects pulling in opposite directions: There will be fewer vehicles, but each vehicle will be driven more. The net effect on total kilometres driven is difficult to predict. Alternative scenarios will have to be developed in order to model a range of potential impacts.

4.14 Shifts in market shares of transport modes

One prediction (Bösch et al. 2018) is that a fully automated transport system will make walking, cycling and public transport less competitive. If individual car ownership remains widespread, this is a reasonable prediction, because a fully automated car will have all the flexibility of a current car, plus the additional advantage that you do not have to drive it. It may be worth noting here that many people love driving and would hesitate to turn the task over to a machine.

Yet, in a fully automated transport system there are large potential gains to be made by making travel less individualised than it is now. The efficiency of the transport system can be greatly improved by using vehicles more intensely, but this presupposes a larger degree of shared mobility than found today. Some forms of shared mobility resemble public transport. Besides, if buses or trains can be run without a driver, the cost of operating them will become lower. This may in turn support higher frequencies. If the next bus or train arrives within five minutes, public transport may actually become more competitive than today.

All of this is of course speculation. Definite predictions are impossible. Some potential impacts of changes in modal split are very difficult to estimate. This applies at least to road safety impacts, since the relevant injuries are very incompletely reported in official accident statistics. Indeed, most injuries to public transport passengers are not the result of accidents, but of falls when alighting or boarding or falls inside the vehicle as a result of e.g. sudden braking. These events are not well reported in accident statistics and any estimate based on official accident statistics is likely to be misleading.

4.15 Changes in commuting distances

Since automated transport is expected to reduce the generalised costs of travel, one potential impact is longer commuting distances. This is typically a long-term effect, but estimates of the long-term elasticity of trip distance with respect to the generalised costs of travel can be found in the literature. These elasticities have, however, been estimated for a non-automated transport system, and it is not clear if they can be applied to a partly or fully automated transport system.

Longer commutes become less burdensome if time can be spent productively or relaxing, rather than concentrated on driving. The impacts of longer commutes on road safety, travel time, energy consumption, etc. depend on which modes of transport are used. For long commutes, it will often be necessary to use more than one mode of transport, as the main mode, say, train, will rarely take you from door to door.

4.16 Energy efficiency of transport

The energy efficiency of transport has been improving for a long time and improvement is likely to continue. Yet, there are many sources of uncertainty regarding the impacts of connected and automated transport on energy consumption and efficiency.

First, if cheaper travel, or cheaper freight transport, induces more traffic, this will partly or fully offset gains in the energy efficiency of each vehicle.

Second, impacts depend on which source of energy is used. Internal combustion engines based on fossil fuel are slowly on their way out; yet connected and automated transport may, at least initially, be based on fossil fuel.

Third, impacts depend on how energy for propulsion of vehicles is produced. Electric engines are clean in the sense that they do not produce emissions the way fossil fuelled engines do. The production of electricity is, however, not always clean. It is necessary to adopt a wide perspective that includes the production of energy for mobility, not just its use by vehicles.

Fourth, it has been proposed that the safety of connected and automated transport could become so high that current crash protection features on passenger cars can be dispensed with. Vehicles could then become smaller and lighter and as a result use less energy.

Fifth, energy use depends on speed. A connected and automated transport system is unlikely to be viewed as attractive if speeds are reduced. Current electric cars, like current combustion engine cars, consume more energy at higher speeds and have an optimal speed that is considerably lower than the mean speed of traffic on the fastest motorways.

Given these uncertainties, analytic decisions must be made about the assumptions to be used in analysis. It is important to rely in assumptions that are as realistic as possible, given current knowledge.

4.17 Vehicle emissions

Vehicle emissions, per kilometre driven, have long been declining. This is likely to continue, but a fossil fuelled engine will never become totally clean. It will always have some emissions. Future changes depend to a large extent on whether electric vehicles will replace current vehicles. Emissions from driving will then be minimised, but the production of electricity could still be associated with emissions.

It is probably safe to predict that a connected and automated transport system will be associated with lower emissions per kilometre of travel than the current transport system. Quantifying the change is difficult.

4.18 Individual accessibility to transport

One of the potential benefits of fully automated transport, is that it can make transport accessible to groups which are now more or less excluded from travelling, or may need to be accompanied on travels. This includes children, people without a driving license or people with functional impairments.

It seems clear, however, that it is only when full automation has been realised that these benefits can be obtained. As long as the need for human intervention may arise, it would not seem advisable to let children or those who are functionally impaired use the automated vehicles. They may not know, or not be able to, intervene and take control should the need for it arise.

4.19 The balance of benefits and risks

The above survey of potential impacts of connected and automated transport systems is not complete. It does not include some potential wider societal impacts like urban sprawl,

new business models for the production and use of vehicles, changes in employment, or lifestyle changes. We have chosen to focus on impacts that can be observed in the transport system. Even with such a limited focus, there are plenty of uncertainties and definite predictions of impacts are impossible.

One potential impact for which a numerical estimate was attempted in this paper, is changes in road safety. It was estimated that a reduction of the number of accidents (given current traffic volume) of about 70 % seemed possible. This is an impressive impact and it is pertinent to ask if it is exaggerated.

It probably is not. It is important to remember that the number of traffic fatalities in most highly motorised countries can probably be reduced by some 40-50 % simply by eliminating three widespread traffic offences: speeding, drinking-and-driving, and non-use of seat belts. Eliminating these risk factors accounts for well over half of the total estimated impact of connected and automated vehicles. The additional impact attributable to full automation is just an accident reduction of some 20-30 %.

It is ironic that mature technology that can eliminate speeding, drink-driving and non-use of seat belts has existed for a long time. Seat belt ignition interlocks were standard in US cars of 1974-vintage, but massive public opposition forced car manufacturers to abandon the technology after just one year (Graham 1989). ISA (Intelligent Speed Adaptation)-systems have been around for about 30 years. ISA-technology is no longer very expensive, as it can be based on digital maps (with updated speed limits) that are part of the GPS-technology any modern car has. Alcolocks have been expensive and invasive, by requiring the driver to give a breath test before starting the car. The breathalysers needed regular recalibration, making the system much too expensive for widespread use. However, sensor technology is progressing rapidly as far as detecting alcohol is concerned, and there has for some years already been talk about an automatic detection system that will sense alcohol from the driver's breath without the need for giving a breath test.

These technologies could be introduced at any time without waiting for the development of fully automated cars and would bring most of the safety benefits that automated cars would bring.

The real issue is therefore whether the additional potential safety benefits of 20-30 % are worth the new risks introduced by automated vehicles. The principal risk is cyberattacks. There are multiple opportunities for such attacks (Parkinson et al. 2017). Extensive and successful attacks could bring automated transport to a full stop. By creating a tightly coupled system, automation dramatically increases the vulnerability of the transport system. Today, a vehicle may break down without much of an impact on the transport system. But if a vehicle connected to other vehicles starts to behave erratically or breaks down, the whole platoon would be affected and might need to be brought to a controlled emergency stop. Vehicle-to-vehicle communication can be disturbed merely by broadcasting noise that makes it difficult or impossible for vehicle sensors to correctly detect signals. Indeed, some recipes for cyber terrorism are so simple that the British government banned publication of one of them, as publishing it could be seen as encouraging crime (Parkinson et al. 2017). No doubt such recipes will find outlets in social media or underground literature that no government can control.

Very little is known about the risk of cyber terrorism and how best to protect society against it. The internet has existed for about 30 years and has survived a number of attacks. Still, some of the viruses spread by hackers have caused extensive damage, and there is an ever escalating "arms race" between hackers and security experts. A similar arms race is likely to develop with respect to automated transport systems.

Securing the system from cyber threats will be difficult and expensive. It is nevertheless not likely that this will be seen as a decisive objection to the development of connected and automated transport. The very extensive reliance on electricity in current society is clearly a source of great vulnerability. If there is a power cut, society grinds to a halt. Anarchy may break out, as seen in the United States during an extensive power cut some years ago. Shops were plundered, as alarm systems were disabled. The scale of the plundering, combined with the fact that there was massive traffic congestion, made it difficult for the police to intervene.

Yet, both electricity and the internet are up and running most of the time. Attacks on the transport system are likely to have local and limited impacts, much the same way that most viruses do not threaten the internet as a whole and most power cuts for electricity remain local.

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